

This is the specialised absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is specific, it is therefore detailed, however, if it is detailed, it is therefore specific. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is detailed. However, if it is detailed, it is therefore specific, however, if it is specific, it is therefore detailed. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is specific. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either detailed or specific.

This set is timed as 22:11, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.